

Interculturalism and Authentic Socio-Cultural Engagement in Contemporary Theatre: From Transnational Collaborations to Interculturalism-from-Below in the Irish Context.

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Intercultural theatre can be defined as a form of theatre that consciously integrates more than one cultural tradition or fosters collaboration between artists from diverse cultural backgrounds in the research, creative process, and presentation of a production.¹ To comprehend the trends and practices of intercultural theatre today, it is essential first to understand the concept of interculturalism, its purposes, ethics, and theoretical complexities. Patrice Pavis observes that offering a clear and concise definition of interculturalism is inherently problematic because of the wide range of approaches and possibilities it encompasses. He describes intercultural performance as the creation of a “hybrid form, by consciously and voluntarily mixing performance traditions traceable to distinct cultural areas.”² Similarly, Jacqueline Lo and Helen Gilbert define intercultural theatre as “a hybrid derived from an intentional encounter between cultures and performing traditions.”³ Julie Holledge and Joanne Tompkins further frame interculturalism as “the meeting in the moment of performance of two or more cultural traditions, a temporary fusing of styles and/or techniques and/or cultures.”⁴ These perspectives highlight the dynamic and transformative nature of intercultural theatre as a site of creative fusion and exchange.

While interculturalism focuses on exchange and synthesis, multiculturalism represents another form of cross-cultural interaction. Multiculturalism recognises the coexistence of multiple cultures within a single society and typically emphasises equality and diversity through social policies that support cultural integration. However, critics argue that multiculturalism can inadvertently reinforce fixed cultural identities and boundaries, fostering division rather than cohesion. Interculturalism, by contrast, not only recognises cultural differences but also valorises them, promoting authentic

¹ This is my own definition in the simplest understanding of intercultural theatre. It is to be considered as a working definition or as an ideational point for exploring the concept.

² Patrice Pavis, “Introduction: Towards a Theory of Interculturalism in Theatre?,” in *The Intercultural Performance Reader*, edited by Patrice Pavis, (New York and London: Routledge, 1996), 8.

³ Jacqueline Lo and Helen Gilbert. “Toward a Topography of Cross-Cultural Theatre Praxis.” *The Drama Review*, 46.3 (2002), 36.

⁴ Julie Holledge and Joanne Tompkins, *Women’s Intercultural Performance*, (London and New York: Routledge, 2000), 7.

interaction and mutual transformation. It emphasises “openness to the ‘other’, active respect for difference, mutual comprehension, active tolerance, validating the cultures present, providing equalities of opportunities, fight discrimination.”⁵ As Martha Nussbaum argues, interculturalism rejects the exclusivist claims of identity politics, particularly the notion that “only members of a given group can understand that group’s perspective.”⁶

Works like Peter Brook’s *The Mahabharata*, Ong Keng Sen’s *Lear*, and Ariane Mnouchkine’s *L’Indiade* are examples of cross-cultural productions that have provoked considerable debate. Some critics regard them as successful models of international intercultural collaboration, while others interpret them as neo-colonial appropriations that centralize Western authorship and epistemic authority. These debates often hinge upon questions of representational ethics, cultural ownership, and the legitimacy of aesthetic borrowing under global capitalist structures. Edward Said’s *Orientalism* remains foundational in this critique, arguing that Western fascination with the “Orient” historically served as a discursive mechanism for legitimising imperial domination, and that representational strategies in the arts often perpetuate this epistemological hierarchy. According to Said, such intercultural encounters are seldom innocent; they are embedded within political and intellectual structures that shape, distort, and subordinate Eastern cultures to Western interpretive frameworks. This dynamic, he argues, constitutes a modern ideological formation akin to racist supremacy, “a kind of anti-Semitism directed against Arabs and Muslims.”⁷ Similarly, Daphne P. Lei identifies the persistence of Hegemonic Intercultural Theatre (HIT), in which Western artistes/institutions exploit “Third World” cultural resources while limiting genuine intercultural exchange. She suggests further that the biggest problem with this phenomenon is that “HIT limits and interrupts cultural flow from the East”, which ultimately consolidates Western discourse.”⁸

Rustom Bharucha extends this critique by situating interculturalism within global economic and political structures. In *Theatre and the World* and *The Politics of*

⁵ Silvio Martinelli, Arne Gillert, Mark Taylor, & European Communities Commission, “Intercultural Learning T-Kit No. 4.”, *Council of Europe*: 2003, 33.

⁶ Martha C. Nussbaum, *Cultivating Humanity: A Classical Defence of Reform in Liberal Education*, (Massachusetts: Harvard University Press, 1997), 82.

⁷ Edward Said, *Orientalism*, (New York: Vintage Books, 1979), 7.

⁸ Daphne P. Lei, “Interruption, Intervention, Interculturalism: Robert Wilson’s HIT Productions in Taiwan.” *Theatre Journal* 63 (2011), 573.

Cultural Practice, Bharucha calls for contextualising intercultural engagements within localised histories of colonialism and globalisation. He urges scholars to move beyond the aesthetic surface of performances and attend to the historical, linguistic, and economic asymmetries that condition intercultural exchanges. His critique of Brook's Mahabharata underscores the dissonances produced when performers articulate culturally specific material in English, resulting in voices "reduced to accents" that render their linguistic textures unintelligible. Bharucha ultimately asks how intercultural practitioners might cultivate respect rather than mere tolerance for cultural difference and whether respect is possible without confronting underlying economic inequalities. Ultimately, he emphasised the pertinent questions of the ethics of representation in the theatre and sought to know if there are alternative modalities of representing the 'Other' with responsibility and engagement.

Brian Singleton further interrogates the term "intercultural" for its tendency to reproduce binary hierarchies between "source" and "target" cultures.⁹ While intercultural exchange ostensibly involves mutual borrowing, Singleton warns that it can inadvertently facilitate "the annihilation of indigenous pre-modern practices by a rapacious First World capitalism. Reflecting on contributions to Erika Fischer-Lichte's Interweaving Performance Cultures initiative, he advocates for a reconsideration of the term 'intercultural' as it is evident that a rethinking of the terminology was necessary."¹⁰ Singleton's appraisal of Ariane Mnouchkine's *Les Atrides* overturns the argument for a central or dominant culture. He argues that "Mnouchkine's interculturalist Shakespeare, far from feminising the Orient from a western male gaze, as suggested by Adrian Kiernander, points out the very emasculation of Western theatrical forms."¹¹ For Singleton, the crucial distinction between cultural appropriation and cultural hybridism, along with the hierarchical relations between West and East, lies in the sincerity of intent, the methodological rigour of the artistic process, and the respect accorded to the cultural materials involved. His reading thus implicitly responds to Said's concerns regarding Orientalism and the politics of representation.

⁹ Brian Singleton, "Performing Orientalist, Intercultural, and Globalized Modernities The Case of *Les Naufragés du Fol Espoir* by the Théâtre Du Soleil" in *The Politics of Interweaving Performance Cultures*, edited by Erika Fischer-Lichte et al. (New York: Routledge, 2014), 85.

¹⁰ Brian Singleton. "Performing Orientalist, Intercultural, and Globalized Modernities The Case of *Les Naufragés du Fol Espoir* by the Théâtre Du Soleil" in *The Politics of Interweaving Performance Cultures*, edited by Erika Fischer-Lichte et al. (New York: Routledge, 2014), 85.

¹¹ Singleton, 95.

Singleton warns that uncritically adhering to the political frameworks of Said or the ethical prescriptions of Bharucha risks producing “hermetically sealed metacultures which do not exchange, trade, or evolve.”¹²

A further conceptual strand of interculturalism relates to Ric Knowles’s definition of it as a “site for the continuing renegotiation of cultural values and the reconstitution of individual and community identities and subject positions.”¹³ Knowles argues that intercultural is preferable to related terms because of its “focus on the contested, unsettling, and often unequal spaces between cultures, spaces that can function as performative sites of negotiation.”¹⁴ This emphasis on the in-between the liminal terrain where cultures confront, transform, and hybridise one another resonates strongly with Erika Fischer-Lichte’s concept of *Verflechtung* (interweaving), which she offers as a more precise alternative to intercultural. Fischer-Lichte critiques the term intercultural for presuming equality between the cultures in contact, a presumption echoed by critics of multiculturalism who point to its insufficient engagement with power disparities.

Interculturalism-from-below

Knowles’s scholarship has consistently centred on intercultural interactions, particularly those arising from immigrant experiences and their contributions to Canadian theatre. Knowles’s work has consistently been grounded in intercultural interactions, particularly on immigrant experiences and their contributions to Canadian theatre. There is a growing interest in such areas, evidenced by the rise in intercultural theatre in Toronto, Canada. Appraising the intercultural scene in the last twenty years in Toronto, Knowles suggests that:

perhaps the most significant development of the past two decades has been the emergence of a vibrant, interdependent ecology of intercultural performance that crosses cultures and disciplines, challenges the hegemony of whiteness on the city’s stages, and reflects the cultural differences that are visible and audible on the city’s streets and streetcars.¹⁵

¹² Singleton, 96.

¹³ Ric Knowles, *Theatre & Interculturalism*, (New York: Palgrave Macmillan, 2010), 5.

¹⁴ Ric Knowles, Introduction: Performing Intercultural Canada. *Theatre Research in Canada*, 30(1-2), 2009, viii.

¹⁵ Ric Knowles, “Multicultural Text, Intercultural Performance: The Performance Ecology of Contemporary Toronto”, in *Performance and the City*. Ed. D.J. Hopkins, Shelley Orr, and Kim Solga edited by D.J. Hopkins, Shelley Orr, and Kim Solga, (UK: Palgrave Macmillan, 2009), 74.

Knowles' analysis identifies four categories of intercultural theatre companies: those whose work is broadly intercultural; those deriving their programming from cultural "homelands"; those dedicated to specific cultural communities; and those producing "new work that speaks across such differences."¹⁶ The latter group comprises individuals whose cultural heritage enables them to occupy binary identities, for instance, those born in or who have acquired Canadian citizenship, regardless of their ethnic lineage. Their work exemplifies the dynamic, locally embedded interculturalism that characterises contemporary Toronto. Based on this categorisation, several immigrant-led theatre companies exemplify similar intercultural engagement in Ireland, using theatrical processes as tools of integration and dialogue. The drivers of the uniquely Irish intercultural integration methodologies were either born in Ireland or have lived in the Republic for a considerable number of years, and are proud of their unique binaries of belonging; being Irish yet still embracing their other identity. The group with hyphenated identities, such as Nigerian-Irish, Polish-Irish, or Brazilian-Irish, etc., and their mainly indigenous counterparts at the forefront of interculturalism in Ireland, are the focus of Charlotte Mclvor's many years of work in Irish society and theatre studies.

Knowles's categorisation provides the conceptual foundation for Charlotte Mclvor's formulation of "interculturalism-from-below". Drawing on the Toronto context, Mclvor focuses on grassroots migrant-led theatre companies in Ireland that generate intercultural discourse not through top-down policy initiatives but through community-based artistic practice. In *Migration and Performance in Contemporary Ireland: Towards a New Interculturalism*,¹⁷ Mclvor documents how immigrant-led companies in Ireland foster innovation and creativity through grassroots intercultural engagement. She argues that in Ireland, "intraculturalism" (mixing between internally differentiated groups within a national context) effectively becomes interculturalism (mixing between majority and minority ethnic groups in varying configurations). Crucially, however, it is

¹⁶ Ric Knowles, *Multicultural Text.*, 75.

¹⁷ Charlotte Mclvor, *Migration and Performance in Contemporary Ireland: Towards a New Interculturalism*, (Ireland: Palgrave, Macmillan), 2016.

the notion of from-below and its meaning in the Irish context that is of particular interest.”¹⁸

Advocating for new models of interculturalism, Mclvor emphasises the developmental necessity of such frameworks, considering the “global rebalancing of financial and cultural power” and the impact of “changing technological and intermedial modes of communication.”¹⁹ She further notes that since the 1990s, often considered the high watermark of intercultural theatre’s earlier theoretical wave, digital modes of communication and experience have become increasingly pervasive and integrated into social life.”²⁰ These shifts have intensified global interconnectedness while simultaneously creating new precarity and uneven wealth distribution, underscoring the need for interculturalism as a multimodal, more democratic site of encounter.

Mclvor’s study examines three migrant-led theatre companies, Arambe Productions, the Polish Theatre Company, and Camino Productions, illustrating how each uses theatre to articulate the socio-cultural experiences of migration and exile. She also highlights the contributions of indigenous artists such as Declan Gorman, Liam Halligan, Donal O’Kelly, Raymond Keane, and Gary Keegan, as well as migrant artists like Kasia Lech (Poland) and Mirjana Rendulic (Croatia). Institutions including Barabbas, Calypso, the Arts Council of Ireland, and Create (the national agency for collaborative arts) are also recognised for their support for intercultural engagement. Mclvor concludes that these individuals and organisations have used their creative practices not only to question and subvert conventional notions of belonging but also to foster collaboration and cross-cultural awareness within Irish society. This, she argues, can be seen from the perspective of “casting, adaptation and translation as interculturalism-from-below in the work of migrant-led theatre companies who have not waited for change to happen from above but made it themselves.”²¹

¹⁸ Charlotte Mclvor, *Migration and Performance.*, 86.

¹⁹ Charlotte Mclvor, Introduction: New Directions? In *Interculturalism and Performance Now: New Directions?* Edited by Charlotte Mclvor and Jason King, (Switzerland: Palgrave Macmillan 2019), 7.

²⁰ Mclvor, *Introductions.*, 8.

²¹ Charlotte Mclvor, *Migration and Performance in Contemporary Ireland: Towards a New Interculturalism*, (United Kingdom: Palgrave Macmillan, 2016), 85.

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